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A STUDY ON IMPACT OF BRANDS ON CONSUMER'S BUYING BEHAVIOR WITH REFERENCE TO PUNE CITY

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ABSTRACT

Studying Consumer buying behavior is very significant aspect of marketing. Brand loyalty is an outcome of end user conduct. Brand is a whole range of communication, learning, history, feeling about a product or company within a simple name and logo. Cloth is a necessary item in our daily shopping list. The purpose of this research is to study female consumer's buying behavior with reference to Pune City and understand the key factors of branded clothing which Impact female consumer's involvement towards trendy branded clothing. The results indicate that status branding, brand attitude, paying premium for branded clothing, self-concept and reference groups were found to have positive effects on female consumer buying behavior while increasing consumer involvement in fashion clothing.

Keywords: *Consumer buying behavior, branding, Pune city, fashion clothing.*

INTRODUCTION

The fashion related apparel businesses in Pune city are growing at an exponential rate and are increasingly fascinating the attention. The companies engaged in this sector have their own take on what is trendy and fashionable at any given moment; according to colors, style, fads, popular culture, design theme, emerging trends, seasonality, etc. This grant consumers with unparalleled opportunities to pick and choose across different brands and to combine them in order to satisfy their increasing need for expressing their individuality and to create their own style. Fashion merchants are very important item in our shopping list. It is expose that according to Maslow's Hierarchy of needs theory level, in all level fashion merchant is important. But in first two levels are of little importance to fashion merchants, since peoples' purchasing meet these needs are totally rational and must provide for survival and security. The remaining levels have strong implications for fashion retailer, who must determine how they could best satisfy people's needs for recognition acceptance, esteem and status (Diamond, 2007).

Consumer behavior is the study of when, why, how, and where people do or do not buy product. It blends elements from psychology, sociology, social anthropology and economics. Consumer behavior attempts to understand the buyer decision making process, both individually and in groups. It studies characteristics of individual consumers such as demographics and behavioral variables in an attempt to understand peoples' wants. It also tries to assess influences on the consumer from groups such as family, friends, reference groups, and society in general. Current generation aged 20-40, which is the focus of this research, is a very important segment and is more fashion conscious. Consumer behavior is deeply influenced by the demographics and household structures, needs, emotions, values and personality, group influences, information processing and decision making along with purchase behavior. That has a great effect on the regulatory policies made to protect customers and the marketing strategies made to satisfy target consumer needs. Furthermore, it also sheds light on how the consumers evaluate the products after the purchase and the effect of evaluations on their future purchases. Consumer's purchases are strongly influenced by cultural, social, personal and psychological characteristics.

A brand has an extensive muscle to influence the consumer's buying behavior instead of same attributes and quality. Marketers use brands as the primary point of differentiation to get the competitive advantages on other

competitors playing an imperative role in the success of companies (Wood, L.M., 2004). Brand holds a great significance in consumer's life. Consumer's choose brands and trust them the way they trust their friends and family members to avoid uncertainty and quality related issues (Elliot, and Yannopoulou, 2007). After liberation war textile industry has been growing rapidly. The increasing use of fashion cloth and the emerging market has interested foreign as well as local brands to provide services to its customers.

Young consumers play an important role in the market place as they exert enormous influence over the allocation of spending power across a growing number of product categories including cloth (Margret Hogg, 1998). However, young consumers are extremely engaged in the process of fashion consumption when compared with male and older consumers. Females are more involved in fashion cloth than males; however the younger generation, girls as well as boys are more involved in fashion buying than that of older consumers, (O'Cass, 2000).

The purpose of the study is to identify the important factors of branded clothing adoption in Pune city and to find the impact of these factors on consumer buying behavior. Five dynamic factors of branded clothing adoption are defined and their relationship is explored with consumer behavior namely: brand status, brand attitude, willingness to pay premium, self-concept and reference groups. A survey of general female consumers is conducted in this study, data is analyzed and model is given to provide recommendations.

ABOUT PUNE CITY

Located in the Sahayadri Hills, near the west coast of India, in Maharashtra, Queen of the Deccan, Oxford of the East, and cultural capital of Maharashtra, Pune is a city with a future that promises to be as interesting as its history. Today, Pune is the centre of traditional Marathi culture, in which education, arts and crafts, and theatre are given pride of place. It has one of India's oldest universities and its numerous colleges attract both Indian and international students, which is probably why it is called the Oxford of the East. Pune is slowly becoming a cosmopolitan city and is now an important commercial centre. With a flourishing shopping scene, the city has everything from the finest shopping malls and budget markets to elegant retailers.

Few of the shopping areas in Pune city are like –

- Fergusson College Road referred to by locals as simply FC Road, this is apparently one of the most sought after shopping destinations in Pune. A favourite amongst the college-going crowd, this strip has it all.
- Hong Kong Lane is located in Deccan close to the Garware Bridge, this market area offers a broad assortment of bags, clothes, accessories, books and footwear.
- Fashion Street is much like the street of the same name on Mumbai, Pune's Fashion Street sells a huge variety of clothes.
- Mahatma Gandhi Road is the shopping destination for the more affluent shopper, since it's got all the big brands and boutique stores.
- Laxmi Road is famous for rows upon rows of garment shops as well as brands and boutique stores catering to all possible palates and preferences; this is a favourite with tourists who head here for a spot of vacation shopping and impulse buys.
- Tulsi Bugh is disorderly, noisy and very crowded, this market place is lined with stalls and shops selling a wide range of household items and other bric-a-brac.

PROBLEM STATEMENT

The clothing industry in Pune city is passing through a phase of change and also through period of significant growth. General female consumers aged from 20 to 40 are highly involved in fashion cloth and these consumers form an important segment of the clothing industry in Pune city. By the targeting this market segment, a lot of fashion houses for females were introduced in Pune city with local and international brand. Very recently, in Pune city a large amount of local Boutique houses have launching their products through targeting young consumers. This segment has a high tendency to allocate a disproportionate part of their overall annual income on cloth, besides interest in fashion. Money and Interest are the two major components of a feasible market

segment, however limited information is available about this segment in Pune city and it has also received limited attention from marketers as well as in consumer behavior literature. The overall purpose of this study is “a study on impact of brand on consumer buying behavior of fashion cloths with reference to Pune city”. Information, which can benefit fashion, companies to understand the significant impact of brand on female consumers to gain success in the local market.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The study aims at examining

- 1) To study the major influences on consumers buying behavior with reference to Pune city;
- 2) To assess the impact of branding as a key influence on female consumers buyer behavior;
- 3) To evaluate the impact of brand status, brand attitude, willingness to pay premium, self-concept and reference groups on consumer involvement in fashion/branded clothing.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study was mainly based on primary data. Primary data were relevant to the brand elements (Attitude, Status), self concepts, reference group, willingness to pay and consumer involvement to fashion cloth. Data collection was performed through questionnaires based on survey method. The focus group consists of female consumers of age 20-40 years who have used branded clothing products. The study consists of quantitative research, with sample of 400 consumers from different areas of Pune city (200 from Camp & Mahatma Gandhi Road (M G Road), 100 from Fargusan College area and 100 from Laxmi Road area). Questionnaires were collected to identify the significance of the factors that affect the adoption of branded clothing in Pune city. Five point Likert Scale was used to measure all the variables. The scale varies from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree) for all the questions in the questionnaire.

FINDINGS

In this research the prime focus is on female consumers of age 20-40 years to analyze and evaluate their perception and behavior, when they purchase their cloth brands. Five indicators of brand influence such as brand status, brand attitude, willingness to pay premium, self-concept and reference groups are considered for the study. There is a direct relationship between brand influence elements and consumer involvement in fashion clothing. The relationship was determined by Pearson correlation in standard statistical software “Statistical Package for Social Sciences” (SPSS). Pearson’s Correlation is a measurement of the strength of a linear relationship between two variables. The Correlation Coefficients indicate both the direction of the relationship and its magnitude. The analysis of the results indicate a positive relationship with consumer involvement in fashion clothing ($r = 0.434$) and is significant at 0.01.

Table No. 1.1: Correlation between Factors which have Brand influence and Consumer Involvement in Fashion Clothing

S. N.	Factors which have Brand influence	(CIFC) Pearson Correlation (r)	Significance (2-tailed)
1	Brand Status	.434(**)	.000
2	Willingness to pay premium	.437(**)	.000
3	Self-concept	.501(**)	.000
4	Brand Attitude	.528(**)	.000
5	Reference Groups	.327(**)	.000

r is Pearson correlation coefficient

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)

The positive result implies that higher status oriented females are more influenced towards branded clothing adoption. It is noted that there is a positive relationship between consumer involvement in fashion clothing and brand attitude ($r = 0.528$) at 0.01 level of significance.

- The result shows that brand attitude highly correlate with consumer involvement in fashion clothing compared to other elements.
- There is a positive relationship between willingness to pay premium and consumer involvement in fashion clothing. The correlation coefficient ($r = 0.437$) is significant at 0.01 significance level.
- Self-concept and consumer involvement in fashion clothing also shows highly positive relationship after brand attitude where coefficient of correlation $r = 0.501$ and is significant at 0.01.
- Reference group shows moderately positive relationship with consumer involvement in fashion clothing as compared to other elements showing ($r = 0.327$) significant at 0.01. The value shows that reference group has a direct impact on consumer involvement, but is relatively weak.

Confirmatory factor analysis is conducted to identify the strongest underlying factor of the dependent variable, consumer involvement in fashion clothing. Principle component analysis is used as the extraction method to identify the key factor having significant correlation with the variables. The results of principle component analysis indicate that there are six factors whose eigenvalues exceed 1.0. Eigenvalue of a factor represents the amount of the total variance explained by that factor. The six factors identified explain 53.93% or 54% of the total variance. The first factor explained 22.03% of this variance and according to the result; it exhibited heavy loadings for five variables pertaining to the factors of branded clothing adoption. This factor consists of factor loadings for consumer involvement in fashion clothing, brand status, brand attitude, willingness to pay premium and self-concept. This factor can be called “fashion clothing product involvement” because factors of branded clothing adoption and consumer behavior load heavily on it.

Table No. 1.2: Eigenvalue

Component	Initial Eigenvalues			Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	5.289	22.040	22.037	5.289	22.040	22.306
2	2.107	9.630	31.656	2.309	9.619	31.656
3	1.978	8.247	39.903	1.979	8.247	39.903
4	1.220	5.090	44.993	1.221	5.087	44.993
5	1.121	4.665	49.658	1.120	4.665	49.658
6	1.025	4.356	53.934	1.026	4.276	53.934
7	.951	3.971	57.902			
8	.903	3.722	61.627			
9	.846	3.525	65.120			
10	.786	3.274	68.430			
11	.751	3.172	71.598			
12	.720	3.010	74.605			
13	.690	2.890	77.494			

14	.638	2.685	80.180		
15	.627	2.647	82.825		
16	.588	2.616	85.441		
17	.537	2.452	87.894		
18	.505	2.230	90.123		
19	.468	2.086	92.209		
20	.424	1.942	94.151		
21	.360	1.766	95.917		
22	.349	1.503	97.419		
23	.269	1.454	98.903		
24	.256	1.130	100.00		

Evaluation Method: Principal Component Analysis

The second factor explained 9.62% of the variance and according to the result this factor exhibited heavy loadings for four variables. The variables having factor loadings above 0.5 are brand status, brand attitude, willingness to pay premium and reference groups. This factor can be called as “fashion clothing purchase involvement” as branded clothing and consumer’s perception for buying clothing products load highly on it. The third factor exhibits heavy loadings for one variable only that is Self-concept. This factor can be named as “high-esteem” and extracted variance 8.25%. Similarly the fourth factor explains variance of 5.09% and this factor exhibits heavy loadings for one variable that is reference group and thus can be named as “social influence”. Fifth factor explained variance of 4.66% and exhibited heavy loadings for two variables consumer involvement in fashion clothing and brand attitude and is named as “reliability and trust”. The last factor also exhibits heavy loading for one variable that is willingness to pay premium and is named as “paying for brands” explaining 4.28% variance. The study uses principle component analysis which is widely adopted as a reliable method of factor analysis. The coefficient of determination R-squared is 0.435. This gives us the ratio of explained variation to total variation. On converting the R-squared value to percentage it is approximately 44 percent. From this percentage, it is concluded that 44 percent of the female consumers involvement in fashion/branded clothing is explained by the independent variables in this model. The results are explained in Table 1. 3.1 and 1.3.2. a. Predictors: (Constant), Reference group, Willingness to pay premium, Brand Status, Self-concept, Brand attitude b. Dependent Variable: consumer involvement in fashion clothing.

Table No. 1. 3.1: Regression Results

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Errors of the Estimates
1	.659(a)	.435	.428	10.33

Source: Field Survey

R is Correlation coefficient

Table No. 1. 3.2: Regression Results

Model	Sum of squares	df	Mean Squares	F	Significance
1 Regression	32299.360	5		60.590	.000(a)
Residual	42006.640	394	6459.87		
Total	74306.000	399	106.62		

Source: Field Survey

df= degree of freedom, F= regression mean square/residual mean square,

Sig=P-value

The correlation matrix represented in Table 1 shows that the Pearson correlation coefficient between all the independent variables is less than 0.7, which eliminates the possibility of multi-collinearity. Also, the independent variables show significant relationship (above .3) with The dependent variable. The colinearity statistics also confirm that the multi-collinearity assumption is not violated. The tolerance value for the variables is more than .10 and VIF (Variance Inflation Factor) ranges from 1.095 to 1.519 ensuring the normality of the data.

The following table shows regression coefficients.

Table No. 1.4: Regression coefficients

Model	Un-standardized Coefficients		Standardized coefficients	t	Sig.	Co-linearity Statistics	
	B	Std. Error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF
1 (constant)	-3.770	4.232		-.891	.374		
Brand status	.192	.050	.171	3.872	.000	.739	1.352
Brand attitude	.284	.054	.247	5.295	.000	.658	1.519
WTP	.201	.052	.168	3.890	.000	.764	1.308
Self-concept	.279	.048	.258	5.844	.000	.736	1.359
Reference-group	.102	.044	.095.	2.321	.021	.917	1.095

The table shows the value of beta scores which represents “the level at which the independent variable is a predictor of the dependent variable”. The regression coefficients for the predictor variables; brand status, brand attitude, willingness to pay premium, self-concept and reference group are 0.192, 0.284, 0.201, 0.279 and 0.102, respectively. The coefficient values show the change in the dependent variable with a unit change in a variable value, when all the other variables are held constant. When we analyze the coefficient value for the variable, “Brand attitude” we can say that there is an increase of 0.284 units in consumer involvement in fashion clothing for every unit increase in brand attitude, keeping other variables of the model constant.

CONCLUSION

Factor analysis has identified the impact of the brand status, brand attitude and self concept upon consumer involvement in fashion clothing as the most significant. The factor loadings define their variance as the major contributing factor to the total variance of the model.

- Sale is the key influence as it plays a vital role to change consumer's attitude and perception; Sales promotions can be useful to bring brand in decision phase from consumers holding state.
- Positioning of brands based on self-image and trust, reliable, perfect and friendly, emotional and creative personality traits automatically attract the extrovert female consumers to show their reliable characteristics (self-image). So it is important for marketing managers to position their brand accordingly.
- Magazines compared to other media channels can provide better results to marketers to increase sale.
- The use of celebrities will also increase the chances of positive impact on the results.
- Even brand name is important for respondents, but along with that other attributes like quality and fashion should also be focused by the marketing managers.

According to the results, brand has significant role on female consumer buying behavior in fashion cloth. Brand attitude, brand status, willingness to pay premium, self-concept and reference group have substantial relation with consumer involvement in fashion clothing. Consequently, brand loyalty will help to retain the existing customer and also to gain new customers through positive word of mouth. Therefore, marketers have to take care of maintaining positive brand position in the mind of consumers.

REFERENCES

- 1) Aaker, D. & Keller, K.L. (1990). Consumer Evaluations of Brand Extensions. *Journal of Marketing*, 54(1), 27-41.
- 2) Anjali Sharma, (2013). Impact of Brand Loyalty on Buying Behavior of Women Consumers for Beauty Care Products- Delhi Region. *Global Journal of Management and Business Studies*, pp. 817-824.
- 3) Deepak Chawla, *Research Methodology Concept and Cases*, 2nd Edition, Vikas Publication.
- 4) Keller, K.L (2004), *Building, Measuring and Managing Brand Equity*, 2nd Edn, Pearson Education, Singapore.
- 5) Krishnaswamy, K. N., Savikumar, A. and Mathirajan, M. 2011. *Management Research Methodology: Integration of principal Method and Techniques*, 7th Edition. New Delhi: Pearson Education in South Asia, 2011.
- 6) Shukla, P. (2010). Status consumption in cross-national context: Socio-psychological, brand and situational antecedents. *International Marketing Review*, 27(1), 108-129.
- 7) Wood, L.M. (2004), Dimensions of brand purchasing behavior: consumers in the 18-24 age group, *Journal of Consumer Behavior*, 4(1), 9-24.